

Electric and Magnetic Properties of some Anthraquinone *o*-Carboxylic Phenylhydrazone Metal Complexes

KAMEL A. EL-MANAKHLY

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, 11884, Cairo, Egypt

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Some metal complexes of anthraquinone with *o*-carboxylic phenylhydrazone (AOCPH) of the types [MLCl₂.3H₂O] and [MLCl₂.2H₂O] have been prepared. The complexes have been studied using electrical conductivity and magnetic susceptibility techniques.

Metal complexes formed with divalent transition metal ions have been investigated¹. Six-coordinated mono- or binuclear complexes of Schiff base hydrazones have also been studied².

The electrical conductivity of organic compounds is an important physical property. Organic conductors have high number of unsaturated C=C bonds forming conjugated system. It is known that the π -electrons of such system are not bound to definite carbon atoms but are capable of moving over the entire molecule.

The present work aims to determine the effect of the complexation of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} (as chloride forms) with anthraquinone *o*-carboxylic phenylhydrazone (AOCPH) on the electrical behavior of the latter. The magnetic properties of complexes have also been studied.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic susceptibility data (Table 1) reveal that all the complexes are paramagnetic.

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC AND ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF ANTHRAQUINONE *o*-CARBOXYLIC PHENYLHYDRAZONE (AOCPH) AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	μ_{eff}	T_c K	E_1 eV	E_2 eV	σ_1^* $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ $\times 10^{-10}$	σ_2^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
[CrLCl ₂ .2H ₂ O]	3.82	390	0.05	0.91	2.40	9.24×10^{-9}
[MnLCl.3H ₂ O]	5.80	405	0.05	0.11	1.69	3.58×10^{-10}
[FeLCl ₂ .2H ₂ O]	5.91	385	0.09	0.49	5.08	7.19×10^{-9}
[NiLCl.3H ₂ O]	3.10	394	0.04	0.29	1.61	5.3×10^{-10}
[CuLCl.3H ₂ O]	1.94	395	0.06	0.26	1.25	4.16×10^{-10}
Ligand	—	364	0.06	0.89	2.52	4.81×10^{-8}

*At 298 K. **At 435 K.

From conductometry, it may be shown that the ligand reacts with the metal cation in stoichiometric ratios M : L and M : L₂ as observed in spectroscopic measurements.

Electrical conductivity : The temperature-dependence of electrical conductivity is shown in Fig. 1. The data reveal a linear trend with inflections appearing at different positions. The general behavior of electrical conductivity obeys the relation,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E/kT)$$

where σ_0 is a constant, E the activation energy of conduction process, T the absolute temperature and k the Boltzmann constant. The values of electrical conductivity (σ) are listed in Table 1. They lie in the range typical of semiconductors³. The break observed in the plot indicates the presence of a phase transition, i.e. two different conduction processes are shown with two activation energies listed in Table 1. Also, the plot shows that the phase conducting in the lower temperature range is of lower energy E_1 than the upper temperature range E_2 . The phase transition observed for the ligand⁴ is most probably associated with two molecular structures (keto-enol form) which exchange the conduction at different thermal stabilities.

Fig. 1. Conductivity of AOCPH and its metal complexes.

The metal complexes exhibit a conventional semiconducting behavior where conductivity shows increasing tendency by raise of temperature. The lower temperature range is the region of extrinsic semiconductors where the conduction is due to the excitation of carriers from donor localized level to the conduction band. At the upper temperature range, the intrinsic region is reached where

carriers are thermally activated from the valence band to the conduction band⁵. This behavior can be attributed to interaction between the electrons of *d*-orbitals and the π -orbitals of the ligand⁶ at upper temperature range. This interaction will lead to localized action of π -electronic charge on the ligand which tends to increase the activation energy. On the other hand, it is known that increasing of complex stability results in decreasing conductivity due to a decrease in π -electron mobility⁷ which agree with the obtained results. The conductivity of the ligand and its metal complexes at 298 K follows the following order : Fe^{III} complexes > ligand > Cr^{III} complexes > Mn^{II} complexes > Ni^{II} complexes > Cu^{II} complexes. They obey Irving-Williams series except Fe^{III} complexes.

Experimental

Anthraquinone *o*-carboxylic phenylhydrazone (AOCPH) was prepared. Then the complexes of AOCPH were prepared and characterized by elemental analyses, ir and electronic spectroscopy⁸.

Electrical conductivity was measured on solid disc (dia

13 mm × 1 mm) mounted between two copper electrodes. The electrical conductivity (d.c.) for the ligand⁴ and its complexes was measured as a function of temperature (298–485 K) using potential probe method^{4,6,7,9}. The data were obtained using Thander TM 353 and HC 3500 T multimeters.

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